

Acoustic Emission And The Fiber/Matrix Interface Failure Progress And Strength In Glass Fiber/Epoxy Laminates

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ABSTRACT

Mechanical and acoustic emission (AE) behavior of E-glass fiber fabric/epoxy laminates were investigated, and combined with transmitted light microscopy observation. Failure progress consisting of several micro-failure mechanisms contributed to characteristic AE behavior. These can be discriminated through frequency spectrum analysis of AE signals detected from the laminates. The estimated results were demonstrated as "damage progress curve" to applied loads, being in good agreement with one optically observed through a microscope. The fiber/matrix debonding strength were examined based on an AE hit rates in the damage progress curve originated by debonding for two laminates fabricated with fibers differing only in their surface treatments.

1. INTRODUCTION

Because of the increase in the variety of fiber/matrix combinations, a greater need is developing for reliable, accurate tests that can measure the bond strength between fiber/matrix. The recognition of the important role of fiber/matrix interface in controlling the mechanical/structural performance of fiber composites has directed much interest to the attempt both mechanical and chemical analyses. The interface is considered as a interphase with a certain thickness. And the constituent components are regarded as modified. Yet, there is little understanding of the thickness and the mechanical properties of this interphase, including the interface strength.

The single fiber composite test[1] and the single fiber pull-out test[2,3] have been often used to characterize the fiber/matrix interface strength. In these tests, model composite samples are used. However, the model samples are with very low fiber contents and with little restraint against matrix material, significantly different from commercial composites. Moreover, woven fabrics composite laminates are often utilized in various application fields of fiber reinforced plastics. The fabric composites include undulation of strands and ply/ply interfaces which have a great influence on mechanical behavior and fracture mechanism in the composites. Consequently, these tests have limits and problems in the estimation of strength of commercial composites. With regard to these points, it should be essentially considered that: (1) The fracture initiation of materials is often controlled rather by microscopic- and local-factors than by macroscopic ones, even for a homogeneous material. (2) The heterogeneous in composite materials is particularly conspicuous

and macroscopically shows a periodicity in laminates. Also, there is a gradient distribution of mechanical properties in a constituent component from the microscopic view point. The complexity of these results in the actual properties in structural fiber reinforced composites.

On the other hand, considering both the development of an excellent composite and the fabrication of a highly reliable composite, it is an issue of wide importance not only to assess the absolute strength[4,5] of the interphase in a model material but also to evaluate the relative strength[6] of that in the structural laminates. From the viewpoint of clarifying the detailed fracture process in composite materials and evaluating the properties of interphase in commercial composite materials, new tests based on NDT should have been attempted for this purpose. However, there has not been enough data generated through the new method to make any quantitative conclusions, although a thermo-acoustic technique was employed to assess qualitatively the strength of the interface bond in commercial composite materials[7]. Aims of the presenting investigations are to contribute to this topic by estimating, based on acoustic emission analysis, the failure progress, in particular interfacial failure sequence during the deformation of structural composite materials. Emphasis is placed upon demonstrating the results estimated through AE analysis as "damage progress curve" to applied loads. Based on an AE hit rates in the damage progress curve originated by debonding, the fiber/matrix interfacial strength were examined for two laminates fabricated with fibers differing only in their surface treatments.

2. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

2.1 MATERIALS AND SPECIMENS

E-glass fiber fabric (Asahi-Schwebell Co., Japan, style #3740) reinforced epoxy matrix composites were produced by a thermal compression method from prepregs. To obtain different mechanical properties of fiber/matrix interface, two types of prepreg were used. The one (specimen #2) contained heat-cleaned glass fabric removed from heat treatment ovens without any further processing and the other (specimen #1, #3) used the glass fiber fabric treated with an aminosilane coupling agent of 1 vol% concentration. Aminosilane is a suitable coupling agent for epoxy resin. The matrix resin used was an epoxy (Yuka Shell Epoxy Co., Japan, FR4) with a dicyandiamide hardener. All of the laminates (14-ply) were fabricated under the same consolidation condition. Under a constant applied pressure of 8.4 kPa, the press temperature was increased to 448 K at a heating rate of 3.7 K/min from preheating at 393 K. After holding at 448 K for 1 hour, followed the curing at 398 K for 10 min. The thickness of sheets was about 3.0 mm, and the reinforcing plain woven fabrics were 0.22 mm in thickness.

Tensile specimens were prepared from these composite sheets. Nominal width of 15 mm was used. The samples, with 0 degree (#1, #2) and 45 degrees (#3) to the warp direction, were 150 mm long and had 30-mm long aluminium reinforcing end tabs glued to each end using a toughened epoxy glue. All the samples had double-edge notches at the center. The notch length-to-width ratio (a/W) was 0.84, and the curvature at the base of the notch was about 1.0 mm. By using these DEN type specimens, early failure was localized around the notches and progressed stably, which led to easy monitoring through a microscope. The results of the observed damage progress were submitted to investigation of qualitative correlation with AE results.

2.2 TEST PROCEDURE

The mechanical testing was performed on a hydraulic servo machine (Shimazu Co., Japan, EHF-ED100KN-20LE). Screw-assisted wedge grips were used to hold a sample. A crosshead speed of

5×10^{-4} mm/s was always used. Since the test section is 85-mm long, the nominal strain rate was 5.9×10^{-6} /s. Tests were conducted in room air at 293 to 298 K. Humidity was not controlled.

Acoustic emission tests were conducted during tensile testing. (1) Two AE sensors (PAC, μ 30s) to measure the ordinary AE parameter were placed on a sample with a spacing of approximately 60 mm at symmetrical portion of the center notch using a silicon grease and vinyl tape. Each transducer output was connected to a 40 dB preamplifier (PAC) with a plug-in filter of 100kHz to 2MHz. The output from the preamplifier was fed to an AE signal processor (PAC, LOCAN L320). The pertinent operating parameters were a system threshold level of 40 dB, the total amplifier gain of 75 dB, a 100 kHz highpass filter, and a dead-time of 1 ms. Signals detected by LOCAN were processed and stored on an internal hard disk. AE parameters stored on the hard disk were post-processed to create graphs of the differential distribution for the standard AE parameters; the peak amplitude, the energy, and the cross-plots of peak amplitude V_p vs. rise time τ_{RA} . The cross-plots V_p vs. τ_{RA} were evaluated as a simple rising-slope ($=V_p/\tau_{RA}$, τ_{RA} is the time reaching to V_p after crossing over a preset threshold level V_{th} of measuring system) distribution, and used to discriminate AE signals. (2) Also, a wide band-width type AE sensor (NORTEC, DZ410-HT) was used, being attached at the side of one of the two sensors to record acoustic emission waveform signals. The waveform signals were recorded by a transient memory (Kawasaki Electronica Co., model TMR-80) with a sampling rate of 50 nsec and 2 k words x 8-bit data to each AE hit, and transferred to an internal RAM disk for off-line post processing. After the test, all of AE waveform data stored on the RAM disk were post-processed to obtain the frequency spectrum of AE signals on a personal computer by using a FFT algorithm. In this process the leading of AE signal was analyzed with a logarithmic window function[8]. The resulted spectrum patterns led to the recognition of AE signals, by which AE source mechanisms were estimated.

3.RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 AE ACTIVITIES AND FAILURE EVOLUTION

Figure 1 illustrates the typical evolution of AE hit activities against test time for the specimen (#1) with surface treated glass fiber during a warp direction loading test up to the fracture. The arrows shown in Fig.1 indicate the load levels (P/PB, PB is the ultimate load) at which AE activity rates increase notably. The entire AE evolution was divided into the following three stages; the first stage in which significant AE started at about 40 % of PB and followed gradual increase with increasing load; the second stage in which the AE hit rates went up at above 70 % of PB and the third stage where the rates became still higher at above 90 % of PB. Such a behavior of increasing in the AE hit rates was also observed in a test for both the warp direction specimen (#2) with heat-cleaned glass fabric and the 45-degree specimen (#3) with surface treated glass fabric, though the load level at which the AE hit rates changed depended on a material.

Transmitted light microscopy observation was combined with AE tests to monitor failure evolution. When the first AE was detected in warp-direction loading test, transverse matrix cracks (TMC) were observed to occur ahead of notch tips. During the first stage that followed when the AE activities gradually increased, TMC not only increased in its number but also became longer with increasing load. In the latter half of the second stage, occasionally, we saw epoxy grain powder flying off from the bottom portion of the notch and, further, this phenomenon occurred more frequently as the final fracture of specimen approached. This was caused by macro-crack produced in matrix close to fiber/matrix debonding near a notch. On the other hand, a distinct whitening near a notch still wasn't observed during the first stage. However, during the subsequent second stage when the AE activities was raised, the whitening was noticed extending toward the loading direction along the warp strand touching a notch tip.

Fig.1 Evolution of AE hits from notched specimen loaded in warp direction.

Under a 45-degree tension test with specimen #3, by contrast, whitening was noticed at the initial stage of AE evolution, beginning from the notched portion along fiber-direction. The whitening extended longer as the load was increased and was found more noticeably than matrix cracks in the 45-degree direction. This whitening was much longer than that found under the warp direction loading test described above.

3.2 DISCRIMINATION OF FAILURE MECHANISMS

The previous discussion suggested that AE behavior was associated with failure evolution. With a transmitted light microscopy, at least, four fracture mechanisms, matrix cracking, fiber/matrix debonding, local delamination and fiber breakage, were observed. In order to estimate the failure progress consisting of these failure modes through acoustic emission technique, what AE parameter can distinguish each specific fracture mechanism was examined by means of the three AE analyses described below.

Figure 2 shows, in three separate graphs, the change of cross-plot of the peak amplitude V_p vs. the rise time τ_{RA} in different stages of failure of AE measured from the 45-degree specimen #3. In this specimen, fiber/matrix debonding was observed most prominently till fracture occurred. The cross-plot graphs show the analyzed result of the apparent rising-slope V_p/τ_{RA} of AE signals. (It should be noted that this figure shows only distribution range of cross-plots of V_p/τ_{RA} , so the total number of plotted points does not correspond to the total number of AE hits.) Cross-plots of V_p/τ_{RA} of AE signals from entire fracture process was divided distinctly into three groups as shown in Fig.2 (d). Referring to the previous study [9], the failure mechanisms corresponding to these three groups are, from the left, (1) fiber breaking, (2) fiber/matrix debonding and local delamination (though, according to the frequency spectrum analysis described later, delamination was not found for the specimen #3), and (3) matrix cracking. Fig.2 (a) and (b) show cross-plot graphs of AE signals obtained from the early stage of failure, considering a low level of AE activities of about 9 % to total AE hits. These graphs revealed that almost all AE produced during the deformation process of up to about 90 % in the loading range results from fiber/matrix debonding or matrix cracking, where debonding is especially dominant. This interpretation of AE supports the failure observation through the video monitor described earlier. Fig.2 (c), on the other hand, gives the V_p/τ_{RA} cross-plot of the AE signals detected during the last 7 % load range ($0.93 < P/P_B < 1$), in which the AE activities rapidly increased. In this Fig.2(c), the group of plots with the highest V_p/τ_{RA} appears for the first time, which indicated that fiber breaking occurred immediately before fracture. A similar analysis was applied to the specimens #1 and #2. The results showed that the failure progress within the load range of $< 0.9 P_B$ was also constructed almost by matrix cracks and

Fig.2 Failure evolution estimated by cross-plot of V_p vs. τ_r for a specimen (#3) loaded in 45-degree direction, (d)=(a)+(b)+(c).

fiber/matrix debonding, and that the initiation load of fiber breaking was 0.93 to 0.95 P_B since few AE due to fiber breaking was detected in early stages of failure (data not shown here).

In Fig.2, we examined the correlation among the distribution ranges of the peak amplitude of the three groups of V_p - τ_r cross-plots of AE signals. In early stages of damage, it seemed that the amplitude distribution range of AE signals generated by fiber/matrix debonding was approximately 5 dB higher than that of AE caused by matrix cracking. However, the difference became smaller as failure progressed. The difference in the amplitude distribution range of AE signals generated by debonding and that caused by fiber breaking was also small. Thus, it was ascertained that the amplitude distribution ranges of AE produced by the three kinds of failure mechanisms were practically overlapped.

Typical peak amplitude distributions for AE signals detected from a specimen #1 are presented in Fig.3. Here, AE signals caused by fiber breaking were extracted by using the criterion of V_p - τ_r cross-plot (i.e. simple rising-slope criterion). The distribution range (indicated by closed bars) due to fiber breaking was 47 to 95 dB, the main range 54 to 76 dB, and was almost overlapped with the distribution range of the entire AE signals (indicated by open bars), in particular, in the amplitude range of 55 to 72 dB.

The frequency spectrum analysis (FSA) of AE signals were clearly estimated the four failure modes: matrix cracking, fiber/matrix debonding, fiber breaking, and local delamination caused in woven fabric laminates (data not shown here). With the analyzed results, **Figure 4** is consisted of four curves indicated in the hit number of AE produced by different failure mechanisms, and shows the damage progress generated during a warp direction loading test on the specimen #1. (This figure is named as "damage progress curve", and will be detailed in the following section.) The figure presents a rapid increase in AE activities generated by fiber/matrix debonding in the load region of $P/P_B > 0.7$ and, where the load is above 0.9, the rise in the activities of AE due to fiber breaking. The latter behavior is quite similar to the evolution assessed through V_p - τ_r cross-plot analysis. The figure also illustrates a fast increase in AE activities caused by local delamination in the load range of $>0.9P_B$. This AE behavior was confirmed by video monitor results that local delamination in area $2 \times 2 \text{ mm}^2$ ahead of a notch tip occurred for a moment.

The previous discussion confirmed that the criterion is not the peak amplitude but the apparent rising-slope or frequency spectrum pattern that is appropriate for distinguishing AE signals caused by debonding. An apparent rising-slope, however, is usually affected by the threshold level of a measuring system. We should convert the apparent rising-slope into a real rising-slope through a statistic processing of data [9,10]. To determine the load at which each of the specific failure mechanisms starts, our investigation is focused on the early failure evolution of AE where the

Fig.3 Amplitude distribution of AE generated by fiber breaking (shown by closed bar).

Fig.4 Damage progress curve of a laminate with surface treated glass fiber during warp direction tensile loading.

number of AE hits was small. The use of AE parameter which makes necessary a statistic processing of data is not suitable. Accordingly, we concluded to employ the FSA in order to estimate the damage progress for each mechanism of failure.

3.3 DAMAGE PROGRESS

Figure 4 demonstrates the whole progression of a typical failure of the specimen #1 in the form of the damage progress curve. Each failure mechanism was distinguished through the FSA [11], which has often been used for discrimination of AE source mechanisms. Note that, due to the limitation of available waveform acquisition rates, the error rate of number of hits increased within the load range of $P/P_B > 0.9$ as the fracture load was approached. Figure 4 showed that AE activities were first observed at a load (P/P_B) of approximately 0.25. This load was slightly lower than the so-called "knee point". Also, the AE at lower loads occurred very erratically from specimen to specimen for the same material. So, it was considered that AE at the initial stage of damage was caused by the notching of the specimen. At $P/P_B > 0.4$, AE activities slowly increased for all the failure mechanisms with increasing load. The AE evolution for the specimen #2 was also similar.

For the specimen #1, AE generated by fiber/matrix debonding was increased constantly at approximately 50% of the increase rate of AE due to matrix cracking in the major stages of AE occurrence ($P/P_B > 0.6$) as shown in Fig.4. For the specimen #2, by contrast, AE due to debonding increased rapidly in the same load range, and occasionally more than 100% of the increase rate of AE generated by matrix cracking was recorded. This difference in the tendency of increase of AE between the specimens was qualitatively confirmed by the difference in the density of matrix cracks displayed on the video monitor.

For fiber breaking, a small number of AE hits were occasionally measured in very early stages of failure. It was presumed that they are due to the initial defects of the fiber, effect of notching of the specimen, etc. Through the entire failure process, AE generated by fiber breaking or local delamination was small in number and most of them occurred immediately before actual fracture. It seemed that a small number of AE due to fiber breakage or local delamination occurring at the load

Fig.5 Fiber/matrix debonding initiation loads corresponded to AE hit rate criteria.

$P/P_B=0.6$ or above triggered the subsequent rapid AE due to evolution of fiber/matrix debonding.

Accordingly, the failure evolution can be more precisely illustrated by means of the FSA technique than by V_p - T_{RA} cross-plot method described in the previous section. It is suggested that the damage progress curve allowed the understanding of not only failure mechanism in each deformation stage but the initial occurrence and the subsequent dynamic evolution of a specific failure mechanism.

3.4 DETERMINATION OF THE FIBER/MATRIX DEBONDING STRENGTH

AE generated by matrix cracking exhibits a rapid and exponential increase at $P/P_B=0.44$ (see Fig.4). This point was estimated as the time when the macroscopic increase of AE generated by matrix cracking occurred. As for AE due to fiber/matrix debonding, it was when the hit rates first increased. These well validated the result of the optical investigation using the video monitor. Compared with the evolution of AE caused by matrix cracking, AE due to debonding gradually increases its hit rates in steps. Taking into account such evolution of AE in early stages of failure, the rapid increase point of AE hit rate will be taken as a parameter for estimating the point at which the fiber/matrix debonding begins and its threshold level will be discussed below.

Figure 5 summarizes the correlation between the applied load and the AE hit rate for each specimen at the times when AE produced by debonding rapidly increases. Data obtained from the same material is grouped, with the closest AE hit rate by which they can be assessed. The threshold level is determined on the following assumptions;

- (1) The time at which the cumulative number of AE generated by debonding is 3 or lower is excluded. Because it was considered that AE measured in early deformation involves signals resulted from the initial defects of fibers and defects during processing on the material, as described in the previous section.
- (2) A hit rate that can provide the minimum scatter of debonding loads obtained for the same material is deduced as the threshold value.

The figure indicated that there are two hit rates each that can provide the minimum scatter of debonding loads: for specimen #1, 2 cpm. at 3.62 ± 0.01 kN and 8 cpm. at 4.22 ± 0.16 kN, whereas for specimen #2, 2 cpm. at 2.87 ± 0.04 kN and 20 cpm. at 3.42 ± 0.19 kN. Accordingly, we took the debonding hit rate of 2 cpm. as the threshold level, which provides smaller scatter of loads. (This threshold level, however, may depends on the testing conditions.) Consequently, it was evaluated that the load at fiber/matrix debonding initiation is 26% higher for the material with the surface treated fiber than for the non-surface treated material. It was also found that the ultimate strength was in average 32% higher for the surface treated specimen, which is very close to the

load at which debonding begins. These results indicate that in structural laminated composites the enhancement of bonding strength at fiber/matrix interface improved the transmitted loads between the fiber and matrix, increasing the strengthening efficiency.

CONCLUSIONS

In order to characterize the failure progression and strength of the interface in structural composite materials, two groups of specially fabricated woven E-glass fiber fabric/epoxy laminates were prepared.

1. Mechanical and acoustic emission behavior of the laminates were investigated, and combined with transmitted light microscopy observation.
2. Acoustic emission behavior was associated with failure evolution. Signals emitted from AE sources caused by matrix crack, fiber/matrix debonding, fiber breaking, and local delamination were discriminated through the frequency spectrum analysis.
3. The estimated results were demonstrated as "damage progress curve" to applied loads, being in good agreement with one optically observed through a microscope.
4. The fiber/matrix debonding strength were examined based on an AE hit rates in the damage progress curve caused by debonding for two laminates fabricated with fibers differing only in their surface treatments.
5. It was evaluated that the load at fiber/matrix debonding initiation is 26% higher for the material with the surface treated fiber than for the non-surface treated material.

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